

Improving the FAIRness of vascular anomaly research data using the ISSVA Ontology

Martijn Kersloot, Philip van Damme, Bruna dos Santos Vieira, Leo Schultze Kool, Ronald Cornet

Vascular Anomalies

Common and rare disorders of blood vessel growth

- From simple “birthmark” to life-threatening entities
- Mainly affect mainly infants, children, and young adults

Classification

Mulliken and Glowacki (1982)

- Support diagnosis, management, and further research of vascular anomalies

Hemangiomas and Vascular Malformations in Infants and Children: A Classification Based on Endothelial Characteristics

John B. Mulliken, M.D., and Julie Glowacki, Ph.D.

Boston, Mass.

... Those difficulties which have hitherto amused philosophers, and blocked up the way to knowledge, are entirely owing to ourselves. That we have first raised a dust and then complain we cannot see.

George Berkeley (1685-1753)¹

The management of cutaneous vascular lesions is hampered by a bewildering nomenclature that has evolved from ignorance of pathophysiology. Textbook classifications offer an array of admixed histologic and descriptive terms. *Hemangioma* has been used as a generic word to describe a variety of vascular lesions with different etiologies and natural histories. The most common tumor of infancy, known as "strawberry," "capillary," "juvenile," or "cellular" hemangioma, predictably undergoes involution. Yet, port-wine stains, which never regress, also are classified as capillary hemangiomas.^{2,6} Unfortunately, the histologic term *caevemas* has been used clinically to describe vascular lesions that involute³ and rarely involute.⁴ Lesions of lymphatic origin, called *lymphangiomas*, grow commensurately with the child, sometimes enlarge,⁵ or may improve with time or even disappear.⁸⁻¹² Hybrid terms, such as *capillary-caevemas hemangioma* and *lymphangiohemangioma*, permeate the literature and further add to the confusion. *Hamartoma* (Greek, *hamartia*, "to sin") is defined as any developmental defect. Albrecht introduced *hamartomas* to describe proliferative lesions of developmental origin, such as neurofibromatosis and hepatic vascular lesions.¹³ However, *hamartoma* is too comprehensive a term—it could be applied to any lesion that histologically shows

a proliferation of cells normally present in a tissue. Contemporary terminology of vascular lesions is enough to befuddle pathologist and clinician alike.

HISTORICAL PERSPECTIVE

It has been argued whether vascular lesions are developmental malformations or types of neoplasia. Dupuytren called them "erectile tumors."¹⁴ Other nineteenth century expressions, such as "naevus maternus" and "stigma metrocelsa," indicted the mother. Vascular lesions were thought to be "produced by the longing of the mother for particular things, or her aversion to them; hence these marks resemble mulberries, strawberries, grapes, pines, bacon, etc."¹⁵ Virchow considered these lesions to be vascular tumors and classified them based on channel architecture as *angioma simplex*, *angioma cavernosum*, and *angioma racemosum*.¹⁶ He believed that one type could transform into another by either cellular proliferation or vessel dilation. Wegner, after studying with Virchow at the Berlin Pathologic Institute, proposed a similar histomorphologic classification of lymphatic swellings that is still used today: *lymphangioma simplex*, *cavernosum*, and *gastroideum*.¹⁷ Wegner believed that these lesions resulted from either lymphatic inflammation and dilation, malfor-

From the Division of Plastic Surgery at the Harvard Medical School, the Children's Hospital Medical Center, and the Brigham and Women's Hospital.
Presented in part at the Third International Workshop for the Study of Vascular Anomalies, on June 6, 1980, at St. Thomas' Hospital, London.

ISSVA

International Society for the Study of Vascular Anomalies (VA)

- Multidisciplinary group of specialists involved in treating VA patients
- Adopted classification
- Classification is revised during international workshops

ISSVA classification for vascular anomalies © (Approved at the 20th ISSVA Workshop, Melbourne, April 2014, last revision May 2018)

This classification is intended to evolve as our understanding of the biology and genetics of vascular malformations and tumors continues to grow

Overview table

Vascular anomalies				
Vascular tumors	Vascular malformations			
	Simple	Combined °	of major named vessels	associated with other anomalies
Benign Locally aggressive or borderline Malignant	Capillary malformations Lymphatic malformations Venous malformations Arteriovenous malformations* Arteriovenous fistula*	CVM, CLM LVM, CLVM CAVM* CLAVM* others	See details	See list

° defined as two or more vascular malformations found in one lesion
 * high-flow lesions

A list of causal genes and related vascular anomalies is available in [Appendix 2](#)

The tumor or malformation nature or precise classification of some lesions is still unclear. These lesions appear in a [separate provisional list](#).

[Abbreviations used](#)

For more details, click on the underlined links

ISSVA classification of vascular tumors 1a

[Back to overview](#)

Type Alt ← for previous view

Benign vascular tumors 1

Infantile hemangioma / Hemangioma of infancy	see details
Congenital hemangioma	GNAQ / GNA11
Rapidly involuting (RICH) * Non-involuting (NICH) Partially involuting (PICH)	
Tufted angioma * °	GNA14
Spindle-cell hemangioma	IDH1 / IDH2
Epithelioid hemangioma	FOS
Pyogenic granuloma (also known as lobular capillary hemangioma)	BRAF / RAS / GNA14
Others	see details

* some lesions may be associated with thrombocytopenia and/or consumptive coagulopathy [see details](#)
 ° many experts believe that tufted angioma and kaposiform hemangioendothelioma are part of a spectrum rather than distinct entities

N.B. reactive proliferative vascular lesions are listed with benign tumors

[Causal genes in blue](#)

ISSVA Classification

- Find and unambiguously classify diagnoses
- Does not allow for structured registration using unique IDs / implementation in software
- → **Need for (new) ontology**
 - ORDO: only rare diseases
 - Classification is updated regularly

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Contents

- Structure of the ontology
- Development
 - From classification to ontology
 - Design decisions
 - Mappings to existing ontology concepts
 - Expert feedback
- Current & planned applications
- Implications & Future work

The ISSVA Ontology

- ISSVA describes **vascular anomalies**, the **causal genes** of such anomalies, and **related vessels**
- ISSVA is organized as a **monohierarchy**
- A total of 202 concepts and 1126 axioms

From Classification to Ontology

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	Simple	Combined *	of major named vessels	associated with other anomalies
Benign	Capillary malformations	CVM, CLM	See details	See list
Locally aggressive or borderline	Lymphatic malformations	LVM, CLVM		
	Venous malformations	CAVM*		
	Arteriovenous malformations*	CLAVM*		
Malignant	Arteriovenous fistula*	others		

* defined as two or more vascular malformations found in one lesion
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Design decisions

- Naming conventions for biomedical ontologies (Schober *et al.*, 2007)
- OBO Foundry ID Policy
 - “Vascular anomaly” → purl.bioontology.org/ontology/ISSVA/ISSVA_00144 → ISSVA:00144
- Hierarchy of the ISSVA classification
 - No residual categories
- Mappings to other ontologies
 - Importing ontologies: unnecessarily large and complex
- Dedicated gene concepts

Mappings to existing ontologies

122 out of 202 concepts were matched to equivalent concepts in other ontologies

Orphanet Rare Disease Ontology
(ORDO)

NCI thesaurus
(NCIt)

SNOMED Clinical Terms
(SNOMED CT)

Human Phenotype Ontology
(HPO)

Mappings to existing ontologies: validation

	ISSVA term	Matched concept	Ontology	Hierarchy
✓ Correct	Sturge-Weber syndrome	Sturge-Weber syndrome	SNOMED-CT	Clinical finding
✗ Incorrect	Other locally aggressive or borderline vascular tumors	NPI - Any Other Aggressive or Agitated Behaviors	NCIt	Activity
⚠ Needs review	Arteriovenous malformation in capillary malformation-arteriovenous malformation	Capillary malformation-arteriovenous malformation	ORDO	Clinical entity

Expert Feedback

- Follow the **OBO Foundry ID Policy**
- Remove/remodel concepts that **cause changes to the meaning of concepts higher up**
- Represent the relation between an anomaly and the vessel type it affects with an **object property**

BioPortal

- Web interface for browsing the ontology
- PURLs
- API access for software developers

International Society for the Study of Vascular Anomalies (ISSVA) Ontology
Last uploaded: April 29, 2021

Summary Classes Properties Notes Mappings Widgets

Jump to:

- Gene
- Vascular anomaly
 - Vascular malformation
 - Combined vascular malformation**
 - Provisionally unclassified vascular malformation
 - Simple vascular malformation
 - Vascular anomaly of major vessels
 - Vascular malformation associated with other anomalies
 - Vascular tumor
- Vessel

Details	Visualization	Notes (0)	Class Mappings (1)
Preferred Name	Combined vascular malformation		
Definitions	defined as two or more vascular malformations found in one lesion		
ID	http://purl.bioontology.org/ontology/ISSVA/ISSVA_052		
comment	defined as two or more vascular malformations found in one lesion		
exactMatch	http://snomed.info/id/400017009 http://www.orpha.net/ORDO/Orphanet_458837		
label	Combined vascular malformation		
prefixIRI	ISSVA_052		
prefLabel	Combined vascular malformation		
subClassOf	Vascular malformation		

Image source: <https://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/ISSVA>

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CONNECT

Application: Data collection and annotation

Registry of Vascular Anomalies

- Implemented in an EDC system to support FAIR data collection
- Diagnosis of the patient registered using the ISSVA classification

(1) Capture diagnosis

(2) Get associated PURL

(3) Generate machine-readable data

Application: Data integration and analysis

- **Information silos** are common in healthcare and rare disease research
- Ontology enables **integrating and analyzing distributed data** sources that contain data about vascular anomalies
- Possible future implementation:
Development of a **virtual platform** by the European Joint Programme on Rare Diseases (**EJP RD**)

Implications & Future work

- Diagnoses can be registered in a **machine-readable manner**
- **Increases the interoperability** of clinical studies and registries that collect data for vascular anomaly research
- **Evaluation** of the increased interoperability of clinical studies
- Showing the **value** of machine-readable diagnosis registration
- Implementation of the ontology in **different settings**

Conclusion

- Monohierarchical ontology based on the **ISSVA classification**
- **Mappings** to existing ontologies
- Capture **machine-readable** diagnoses of vascular anomaly patients
- **Increases interoperability** between clinical studies and registries
 - Contributes to **FAIRer** vascular anomaly research

Thank you

Full paper

bit.ly/issva-paper

Ontology

bit.ly/issva-ontology

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The International Society for the Study of Vascular Anomalies (ISSVA) ontology

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ABSTRACT

The International Society for the Study of Vascular Anomalies (ISSVA) provides a classification for vascular anomalies that enables specialists to unambiguously classify diagnoses. This classification is only available in PDF format and is not machine-readable, nor does it provide unique identifiers that allow for structured registration. In this paper, we describe the process of transforming the ISSVA classification into an ontology. We also describe the structure of this ontology, as well as two applications of the ontology using examples from the domain of rare disease research. We used the expertise of an ontology expert and clinician during the development process. We semi-automatically added mappings to relevant external ontologies using automated ontology matching systems and manual assessment by experts. The ISSVA ontology should contribute to making data for vascular anomaly research more Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR). The ontology is available at <https://bioportal.bioontology.org/ontologies/ISSVA>.

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1. Introduction

Vascular anomalies represent a broad spectrum of common and rare disorders of blood vessel growth, ranging from a simple “birthmark” to life-threatening entities, which affect mainly infants, children, and young adults [1,2]. To support diagnosis, management, and further research of vascular anomalies, Mulliken and Glowacki created a comprehensive classification system for vascular anomalies [3]. This classification system, published in 1982, distinguishes between vascular tumors (formerly referred to as *hemangiomas*) and vascular malformations.

The ISSVA, adopted this classification in 1996. ISSVA, founded in 1992, is the society for specialists of various medical disciplines involved in the treatment of patients afflicted with vascular anomalies [2]. During international ISSVA workshops, the classification is revised by specialists, as the understanding of the

biology and genetics of vascular anomalies continues to grow [4]. The latest revision of the classification was published in 2018 [4] and is available as an interactive PDF (Fig. 1).

The interactive PDF contains hyperlinks to several sections of the classification and allows specialists to easily find anomalies by their type (e.g. a *Congenital hemangioma* is a *Benign vascular tumor*) or their causal gene (e.g. the gene *VEGFC* is associated with *Primary hereditary lymphedema*). While the PDF allows specialists to find and unambiguously classify diagnoses, it does not allow for structured registration of these diagnoses using unique identifiers, nor implementation in software systems, such as Electronic Health Records (EHRs) and Electronic Data Capture (EDC) systems. To make the data for vascular anomaly research more Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) [5], it is important that these diagnoses are registered in a structured manner.

A majority of the vascular anomalies present in the ISSVA classification are rare diseases. In line with the FAIR principles, the European Platform on Rare Disease Registration recognizes the importance of structured registration and therefore strongly recommends the use of the Orphanet nomenclature of rare diseases for registering diagnoses in their Common Data Elements (CDEs) [6]. Each disease in this nomenclature is attributed a

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